

Summer Internship Project
Report

Full Stack Development at Glostars Oy

Submitted by

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Certificate of Approval

The internship report entitled “Full Stack Development at Glostars Oy” is submitted to the Computer Science and Engineering, University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh, Dhaka in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the project course of Bachelor of Science.

Name of the guide
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Abstract

This internship report focuses on my contribution towards Glostars Oy as an intern and achievements from this internship program. It provides detail on my activities at this company, technical and professional achievements what I have learnt from observing the other IT professionals.

This report also provide the working process of Web development and Mobile development at Glostars Oy. The three-month internship program was carried out at Glostars Oy I was given the responsibility of learning, implementing and analyzing the results of Web development. This report explains my completed projects and ongoing activities in this company as an intern member of WEB team.

The steps of software requirements analysis, software planning, implementation, testing phase and maintaining phase were followed and documented for every project. Finally, this report concludes with the achievements as an intern in terms of professionalism and attitude that highlights the values of the internship program. Recommendations for the prospective interns are also provided.

Contents

1	Objective	1
2	Introduction	2
2.1	Background of the study	2
2.1.1	Technology Stack	3
2.2	Statement of Problem/Issue	4
3	Company Profile	5
3.1	What Glostars Offer	5
3.1.1	Mutual Follower Photo	5
3.1.2	Public Photo	6
3.1.3	Competition Photo	6
3.1.4	Different Things of Glostars	6
3.1.5	Achievements of Glostars	6
3.2	Services and Products	6
3.2.1	Services	7
3.2.2	Products	7
3.3	Departments	8
4	Technologies	9
4.1	Hardware	9
4.1.1	Microsoft SQL server 2014	9
4.1.2	IIS Server	10
4.2	Software	12
4.3	Technology Explanation	13
4.3.1	Microsoft visual studio 2013	14
4.3.2	Microsoft Visual Studio Code	14
4.3.3	Html5	15
4.3.4	CSS	15
4.3.5	Javascript	16
4.3.6	Jquery	16

4.3.7	Bootstrap	16
4.3.8	ReactJs	17
4.3.9	Some Features of ReactJs	17
5	Work Done	19
5.1	Project Background	19
5.2	Project Design	20
5.2.1	System Overview	20
5.2.2	Client Applications Layer	21
5.2.3	API Gateway and Load Balancer Layers	21
5.2.4	Backend Microservices Layer	21
5.2.5	Data Storage and External Services Layers	22
5.3	Environment Setup and Coding Style	22
6	Implementation	27
6.1	The Interview Task	27
6.2	Task 1	29
6.2.1	Problem 1	29
6.2.2	Solution 1	29
6.3	Task 2	31
6.3.1	Problem 1	31
6.3.2	Solution 1	31
6.3.3	Problem 2	32
6.3.4	Solution 2	32
6.3.5	Problem 3	32
6.3.6	Solution 3	32
6.3.7	Problem 4	33
6.3.8	Solution 4	33
6.3.9	Problem 5	33
6.3.10	Solution 5	33
6.3.11	Problem 6	34
6.3.12	Solution 6	34
6.4	Task 3	34
6.4.1	Problem 1	35
6.4.2	Solution 1	35
6.4.3	Problem 2	35
6.4.4	Solution 2	35
6.4.5	Problem 3	35
6.4.6	Solution 3	36
6.4.7	Problem 4	36
6.4.8	Solution 4	36

6.4.9	Problem 5	37
6.4.10	Solution 5	37
6.4.11	Problem 6	37
6.4.12	Solution 6	37
6.4.13	Problem 7	37
6.4.14	Solution 7	37
6.4.15	Problem 8	38
6.4.16	Solution 8	38
6.4.17	Problem 9	38
6.4.18	Solution 9	38
6.4.19	Problem 10	40
6.4.20	Solution 10	40
6.5	Task 4	40
6.5.1	Problem 1	40
6.5.2	Solution 1	41
6.5.3	Problem 2	41
6.5.4	Solution 2	41
6.5.5	Problem 3	42
6.5.6	Problem 4	42
6.5.7	Problem 5	42
6.5.8	Problem 6	42
6.5.9	Solution 3 4 5 6	42
6.5.10	Problem 7	43
6.5.11	Solution 7	43
7	Conclusion and Recommendations	45
7.1	Conclusion	45
7.2	Recommendations	46
7.2.1	Recommendation to their services	46
7.2.2	Recommendation to software & hardware services	46
7.2.3	Recommendation to other services	46
	Acknowledgements	47
	Declaration	48
	References	49

Chapter 1

Objective

The main objectives of the report is to familiarize with overall activities of the web development section of the Glostars Oy as well as its products, customers, standard practices and their success stories.

To know about the challenges which are faced in the software industry, to evaluate and analyze the software development systems in Glostars, to get the real life experience in web development sector, to know about the coding conventions and style, to get the experience of the team working, to explain my job responsibility as an intern and narrate different lessons learnt while working as an intern at Glostars. My achievements as an intern, especially focusing my nonacademic and professional achievements, self assessments and company evaluation.

Chapter 2

Introduction

2.1 Background of the study

I worked as an ASP.NET full stack developer intern in Glostars Oy Company. Glostars Oy is a software development Finnish company, having business and interest in Social Media software solutions in Finland. They have only one project just like Facebook. Their Main users are photographers[1].

Figure 2.1: Glostars Opening Page

Though Glostars Oy works almost every platform of information technology, I got the chance of working with developer team. More specifically I did Web Features development there. During my internship I developed front-end development of their four page and also used the front-end framework for working the front-end side faster. I used the Reactjs technology for doing the work faster. All of my work was now publish as a live server into the glostars website Figure 2.1. This website is responsive for any screen size.

Developing this web features I work with some Web platform languages

such as Asp.net Mvc, html, css, bootstrap, javascript, jquery, SignalR and c#. I use Asp.net Mvc and SignalR for creating the chatting application feature. For design or the front-end side I use html, css and javascript and the ReactJs library. I use font color, background color, font-size, font-family, margin, padding etc properties to CSS.

I also use some dependencies which is add some features that I can use in my project. I use Dependencies which works with Asp.net MVC to enhance Object Relational Mapping using entity framework and make them more dynamic. I made glostars web apps full responsive that all of the screen resolution support it for this I used bootstrap.

I used material design code with XML which verify the activity is looking perfect for users. I also involved with two other projects one is Chat in Room and another is Pocket Bank. I worked as a android developer in these projects. I tried to use all my coding skills what I have learned to make those apps best and get user satisfaction. I followed best coding practice and coding conventions within my knowledge.

Into this Internship period as I already mentioned I am a Full stack developer at Glostars Oy. So their maximum website work task is given to me. When they give me there existing website for solving me. I found they have used so many technologies into their website. As a Background of the study I am going to describe those technologies into this section.

2.1.1 Technology Stack

The Glostars website employs the following technology stack:

AngularJS 1: Front-end JavaScript framework

ASP.NET MVC: Server-side web framework

ASP.NET WEB API: Framework for building HTTP services

Bootstrap 3: Front-end framework for responsive design

HTML, CSS, JavaScript: Core web development technologies

jQuery: JavaScript library for DOM manipulation

2.2 Statement of Problem/Issue

When I start working at Glostars website I found out so many problems they had into their website. There is color miss match, function, validation problem into their website. Some of the main problems I am going to describe into the bullet point below:

- They have style sheet that means Css problem into the Glostars website.
- The website is responding so slowly.
- One page and another page didn't connect properly because there is some functional problem into their website.
- They have new design which has navigation bar but its not working properly at that time.
- They didn't have any chatting application into their website.
- The responsive design of the glostars website not fixed properly so that it wat not response in every resulation size of the screen.
- Chatting application was not developed as end to end encryption.
- Login functionaliy was not declared so clearly into the code file.
- Some of the page of glostars website was not dynamic.

Chapter 3

Company Profile

Glostars is a website where we can share photos which allows individuals , groups or organizations to share pictures to the global audience. It has competition feature which is running on regular basis. Into This website a user can share their picture and can win the exciting prizes . They can earn prizes based on community voting. Glostars is not only a photo sharing platform but also people can use it for sharing the photos to their friend and other persons too. A User has full freedom for using this website for their sharing moments.

3.1 What Glostars Offer

By using this glostars website a user can share photo globally also they can rate the pictures and grow network and can create a global community. A user can share his or her picture in three ways.

- Mutual Follower Photo.
- Public photo.
- Competition photo.

3.1.1 Mutual Follower Photo

Into this section a user can share his or her picture mutually . when both user following each other then it will be a mutual follower and they can share their mutual photo to them.

3.1.2 Public Photo

Into this section a user can share his or her picture around the globe . All of the user of glostars can see his or her sharing photo.

3.1.3 Competition Photo

Into this section a user can upload his or her best picture for the competition and can win the prizes. Basically glostars chose a best user photo by searching the highest voting or starred picture every week. They have several prize section, they can give monthly ,weekly prizes . Also at the end of the competition term that means every 4 month in a calendar glostars give a best and big prize to the winner user . At the end of the competition term glostars organize a Photo Exhibition with the top 50 pictures of the competition.

3.1.4 Different Things of Glostars

- They reward and reward users or peoples to photography through prizes and spot exhibitions.
- They aware of or do not support he copyrights of the shared picture.
- They are better controller for sharing the user pictures to the online.

3.1.5 Achievements of Glostars

Basically it's a social media website and their main vision is to communicate people with the photography by heart. They start their journey in 2016. In this minimum time they have prized or awarded more than 80 pictures which is collected from different parts of the world. Also they have organized 3 international photo exhibitions in Finland portraying over 150 top voted pictures.

3.2 Services and Products

I was assigned to Glostars Oy as an intern. Glostars Oy is a social media service company, having business presence and interest in client's satisfaction. The company has been established in Finland since 2016 and operating as a social media organization. Its goal is to find out the best photographers and their pictures and work hard to create the environment into the internet as a website like Facebook. They have only one product which is Glostars

website and they targeted that it will be a huge software or environment like facebook only for photographers.

3.2.1 Services

Service of the Glostars is all for photographers. They have collect all the unique photos which is measured by the vote of the users. Facebook has the like option for count the likes, but Glostars have the vote option for counting the vote for specific picture Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Voting Star of Image

They count the star mark vote and then give prize to the winner photographer for his or her picture. They organize also exhibition program which is called Glostars exhibition. In every 4 month after they organized this exhibition where they showed top 100 picture which is top voted or winner.

3.2.2 Products

Right now they have two products one is web and another is mobile app that is android app.

- Web App(Figure 3.2).
- Android App(Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.2: Web Application

Figure 3.3: Android Application

3.3 Departments

Although It is a social media website so they have only one product into the market just like facebook that is Glostars where all of the photography picture and photographers are connected with each other. Also they can share their photos into that website. They have a website called Glostars.com and a android app called Glostars beta in Google play store. And the IOS app is in under development.

So there is three department.

- Web App Department.
- Android App Department.
- IOS App Department.

Into the Web App the address of the Http link is www.glostars.com . It is there web product which is used by at least 4 thousand users. All of the users are also into the mobile app. Into this section they have 2 web developer and 1 intern which is mine. Also they have 2 Front-end web developer who are working into this web department. Android App basically recently launched in October. Now it is one of the favorites app for the Glostars users. They can take instant shot from their phone and can install upload it to the server. Into this android app section they have 3 android developer. Into the IOS department there is 3 IOS developer who are working and developing the IOS App.

Chapter 4

Technologies

Glostars Oy really love technology stack. This is partly because without them, This Company is only a handful of concepts, but mostly because they are fun to work with. Glostars Oy strives to ensure that the fun is always in the equation. The technology mentioned below helps us make what we make, and we are glad we picked them amongst thousand other options.

4.1 Hardware

Into the Hardware section I will discuss which technologies basically used in Glostars hardware. For hardware support Glostars basically deal with Microsoft Company. Microsoft give them the server , database and space for running their total software. So the technologies which is work as hardware given by the Microsoft company are given below:

- Microsoft SQL Server 2014
- IIS server

4.1.1 Microsoft SQL server 2014

Why they used Microsoft Sql server 2014 because their website is made in C# which is totally depended on Microsoft technology. Glostars website used Asp.net Mvc with C# programming languages and its support Microsoft sql server so that's why it is mandatory to use this server. Into this All of the data is stored into it. All of the user data , pictures , message and all of the data which is stored into this SQL server[2].

SQL Server is a central part of the Microsoft data platform. SQL Server is an industry leader in operational database management systems (ODBMS) Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: MS Sql server 2014

4.1.2 IIS Server

Why IIS Server is need for Glostars website. Basically its so important for running the website into the Http protocol. Main thing is that this server opens the http port for connecting the website into the internet Figure 4.2. Internet Information Services (IIS, formerly Internet Information Server) is an extensible web server created by Microsoft for use with the Windows NT family. IIS supports HTTP, HTTP/2, HTTPS, FTP, FTPS, SMTP and NNTP. It has been an integral part of the Windows NT family since Windows NT 4.0, though it may be absent from some editions (e.g. Windows XP Home edition), and is not active by default[3].

There are so many versions of IIS server and it is updating day by day its features.

- IIS 1.0 was initially released as a free add-on for Windows NT 3.51.
- IIS 2.0 was included with Windows NT 4.0.
- IIS 3.0, which was included with Service Pack 2 of Windows NT 4.0, introduced the Active Server Pages dynamic scripting environment.
- IIS 4.0 was released as part of the "Option Pack" for Windows NT 4.0. It introduced the new MMC-based administration application.

- IIS 5.0 shipped with Windows 2000 and introduced additional authentication methods, support for the WebDAV protocol, and enhancements to ASP. IIS 5.0 also dropped support for the Gopher protocol.
- IIS 5.1 was shipped with Windows XP Professional, and was nearly identical to IIS 5.0 on Windows 2000.
- IIS 6.0, included with Windows Server 2003 and Windows XP Professional x64 Edition, added support for IPv6 and included a new worker process model that increased security as well as reliability.
- IIS 7.0 was a complete redesign and rewrite of IIS, and was shipped with Windows Vista and Windows Server 2008. IIS 7.0 included a new modular design that allowed for a reduced attack surface and increased performance. It also introduced a hierarchical configuration system allowing for simpler site deploys, a new Windows Forms-based management application, new command-line management options and increased support for the .NET Framework. IIS 7.0 on Vista does not limit the number of allowed connections as IIS on XP did, but limits concurrent requests to 10 (Windows Vista Ultimate, Business, and Enterprise Editions) or 3 (Vista Home Premium). Additional requests are queued, which hampers performance, but they are not rejected as with XP[4].
- IIS 7.5 was included in Windows 7 (but it must be turned on in the side panel of Programs and Features) and Windows Server 2008 R2. IIS 7.5 improved WebDAV and FTP modules as well as command-line administration in PowerShell. It also introduced TLS 1.1 and TLS 1.2 support and the Best Practices Analyzer tool and process isolation for application pools.
- IIS 8.0 is only available in Windows Server 2012 and Windows 8. IIS 8.0 includes SNI (binding SSL to hostnames rather than IP addresses), Application Initialization, centralized SSL certificate support, and multicore scaling on NUMA hardware, among other new features.
- IIS 8.5 is included in Windows Server 2012 R2 and Windows 8.1. This version includes Idle worker-Process page-out, Dynamic Site Activation, Enhanced Logging, ETW logging, and Automatic Certificate Rebind.
- IIS 10 is included in Windows Server 2016 and Windows 10. This version includes support for HTTP/2.

GLOSTARS.COM

Technology Profile

Figure 4.2: ISS server used by Glostars

4.2 Software

This software section is one of the most important section for any IT Company or Software technology. Because there are so many technology and software which is used for making this application. Glostars Oy also have their technology which they using for making their website, mobile app, and IOS app. I am going to describe all of this technology which brief details into this section.

For Web App Technologies: glostars used some software and IDE for development purpose. visual studio was used for coding backend of software and the visual studio code was used for frontend development because it was lightweight.

Software or IDE:

- Microsoft Visual Studio 2013.
- Microsoft Visual Studio Code.

Programming Languages: it is one of the core part for developing the software. different programming language is used for various purpose. in this case mostly JavaScript programming language is used for frontend development and c# programming language is used for backend development.

Front-End Side: glostars used the html5 and Css for page design javascript and jquery for functional effect on the website, bootstrap for page responsiveness and Reactjs for state management.

- Html5
- Css

- Javascript
- JQuery
- Bootstrap
- ReactJs

Back-End Side: they used the model view controller framework in the backend side with Asp.net technologies. Most of the code was written in c# code.

- Asp.net mvc 4.5
- Asp.net webapi
- SignalR
- LinQ
- Entity Framework
- Code First Migration
- C#

For Mobile App or Android App technologies: Android Studio

- Java
- React-native
- XML

IOS App Technologies:

- Swift
- Objective-c

4.3 Technology Explanation

Into the website they used programming languages, Frameworks, Design components language and many more. So I am going to describe all of this technology one by one.

4.3.1 Microsoft visual studio 2013

Microsoft Visual Studio is an integrated development environment (IDE) from Microsoft (Figure 4.3). It is used to develop computer programs, as well as web sites, web apps, web services and mobile apps[5].

Figure 4.3: MS visual studio 2013

4.3.2 Microsoft Visual Studio Code

Visual Studio Code is a source code editor developed by Microsoft for Windows, Linux and macOS (Figure 4.4). It includes support for debugging, embedded Git control, syntax highlighting, intelligent code completion, snippets, and code refactoring[6].

Figure 4.4: Visual Studio Code IDE

4.3.3 Html5

HTML5 is a markup language used for structuring and presenting content on the World Wide Web(Figure 4.5). It is the fifth and current major version of the HTML standard[7].

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
<title>Page Title</title>
</head>
<body>

<h1>This is a Heading</h1>
<p>This is a paragraph.</p>

</body>
</html>
```

Figure 4.5: HTML5 Code snippet

4.3.4 CSS

Cascading Style Sheets is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of a document written in a markup language[8]. (Figure 4.6) showing us the attribute section of CSS.

CSS Syntax

A CSS rule-set consists of a selector and a declaration block:

Figure 4.6: CSS Code declaration

4.3.5 Javascript

JavaScript, often abbreviated as JS, is a high-level, dynamic, weakly typed, prototype-based, multi-paradigm, and interpreted programming language[9]. (Figure 4.7) showing us the code snippet of JavaScript.

```
<button onclick="disableElement()">Disable</button>

<script>
function disableElement() {
    document.getElementById("btn01").disabled = true;
}
</script>
```

Figure 4.7: Javascript code snippet

4.3.6 JQuery

jQuery is a cross-platform JavaScript library designed to simplify the client-side scripting of HTML. It is free, open-source software using the permissive MIT License[10].(Figure 4.8) showing us the code snippet of JQuery.

```
<script>
$(document).ready(function(){
    $("p").click(function(){
        $(this).hide();
    });
});
</script>
</head>
```

Figure 4.8: JQuery code snippet

4.3.7 Bootstrap

Bootstrap is a free and open-source front-end web framework for designing websites and web applications[11].(Figure 4.9) showing us the code snippet of Bootstrap.

```
<div class="container">
  <div class="row">
    <div class="col-sm-4">
      <h3>Column 1</h3>
      <p>Lorem ipsum dolor..</p>
      <p>Ut enim ad..</p>
    </div>
```

Figure 4.9: Bootstrap code snippet

4.3.8 ReactJs

ReactJs is a Javascript library for building user interfaces. It is maintained by Facebook, Instagram developers and communities. React allows developers to create large web-applications that use data and can change over time without reloading the page. It aims primarily to provide speed, simplicity, and scalability[12].

4.3.9 Some Features of ReactJs

One way Data Flow : To use React to its greatest potential, Properties (or props), ideally a set of immutable values, are passed to a component's render function. A component should not directly modify any properties passed to it, but should be passed callback functions that instead modifies the store creating a single source of truth. This mechanism's promise is expressed as "properties flow down; actions flow up". The described mechanism is an architecture called Flux. Many Flux alternatives have been created since its inception however the community has moved toward Redux.

Virtual Dom : Another notable feature is the use of a "virtual Document Object Model", or "virtual DOM". React creates an in-memory data structure cache, computes the resulting differences, and then updates the browser's displayed DOM efficiently. This allows the programmer to write code as if the entire page is rendered on each change, while the React libraries only render sub components that actually change[13].

JSX : React components are typically written in JSX, a JavaScript extension syntax allowing quoting of HTML and using HTML tag syntax to render sub-components. This is a React-specific grammar extension to JavaScript like the now-defunct E4X. HTML syntax is processed into JavaScript calls of the React framework. Developers may also write in pure JavaScript. JSX

is similar to another extension syntax created by Facebook for PHP, XHP. JSX looks like regular HTML. An example of JSX code:

```
import React from 'react';
class App extends React.Component {
  render() {
    return (
      <div>
        <p>Header</p>
        <p>Content</p>
        <p>Footer</p>
      </div>
    );
  }
}
export default App;
```

Chapter 5

Work Done

5.1 Project Background

As I already described that I am working as an intern in Glostars. In this company my role is that I am website developer of the Glostars. For developing their website I worked with the technology called Asp.net Mvc which is written with the C# programming Language.

So in Chapter 2 the problem and Issue section I already describe how many problem they have into their website. As a result they mark the problems and then give me to fix all of that problems. So Into the internship period I have done so many works. I am going to describe all of this work into this working project section. At first I solve so many front-end work, re-design their website also change some technology they had not before into their website such as bootstrap3 to bootstrap4. Also they had responsiveness problem into their website.

I solved At least 40 bugs of their website and every bugs give me a new knowledge. Each of every bugs gives me a new name of a development technology.

When I talk with the Glostars company they also took a interview of me and also give me a task which called a login register system for their website and I successfully passed that task and then they hired me.

I am going to describe all of this working projects into the implement section one by one.

5.2 Project Design

5.2.1 System Overview

The proposed software system implements a multi-tier client-server architecture designed to support three distinct client platforms—web browsers, Android devices, and iOS devices—through a unified backend API. This architectural approach ensures scalability, maintainability, and platform independence while delivering a consistent user experience across all devices. The system is structured in layers, each with specific responsibilities that work together to process user requests efficiently and reliably[14].

Figure 5.1: Project Design

5.2.2 Client Applications Layer

The client applications layer represents the frontend components that users directly interact with. The web application is typically built using modern JavaScript frameworks like React, Angular, or Vue.js, providing a responsive experience across desktop and mobile browsers. The Android application, developed natively using Kotlin or Java, leverages the Android SDK to deliver optimal performance on Android devices. Similarly, the iOS application, built with Swift, utilizes native iOS frameworks to ensure seamless integration with Apple's ecosystem. All client applications communicate with the backend through HTTPS/REST APIs, implementing local caching strategies and supporting offline capabilities where appropriate. Mobile applications additionally integrate with platform-specific push notification services to keep users engaged with timely updates[15].

5.2.3 API Gateway and Load Balancer Layers

The API gateway serves as the single entry point for all incoming client requests, functioning as the system's front door. This critical component handles essential cross-cutting concerns including authentication, rate limiting, CORS management, request routing, and SSL termination. By centralizing these functions, the gateway simplifies client implementations and ensures consistent security enforcement across all access points. Following the gateway, the load balancer distributes incoming traffic across multiple instances of backend services, preventing any single service instance from becoming overwhelmed. It continuously monitors service health, automatically redirecting traffic away from failing instances and enabling horizontal scaling during periods of high demand[16].

5.2.4 Backend Microservices Layer

The business logic is implemented through a set of specialized microservices, each responsible for a specific domain of functionality. The authentication service manages user registration, login, session management, and security policies using JWT tokens and OAuth2 integration. The business logic service contains the core application functionality, enforcing business rules, validating data, and orchestrating complex workflows. File handling operations are managed by the file service, which oversees uploads, downloads, storage management, and integration with content delivery networks. The notification service coordinates all communication with users through push notifications, emails, and SMS messages, while the analytics service collects and

processes user behavior data and performance metrics[17].

5.2.5 Data Storage and External Services Layers

The system employs multiple storage solutions optimized for different types of data. The primary relational database, typically PostgreSQL or MySQL, stores structured data such as user information, application state, and transactional records, ensuring ACID compliance for critical operations. For high-performance needs, Redis provides in-memory caching for session data and frequently accessed information. Large files and binary data are stored in cloud storage solutions like AWS S3, which offer scalability and cost-effectiveness. The architecture also integrates with various external services including push notification platforms (Firebase Cloud Messaging, Apple Push Notification Service), payment gateways (Stripe, PayPal), email delivery services (SendGrid, Amazon SES), and analytics tools (Google Analytics) to extend functionality without reinventing complex capabilities[18].

5.3 Environment Setup and Coding Style

At the beginning we need some tools or IDE for our writing code environment. Asp.net is a Microsoft product so they have their own IDE called Microsoft visual studio. So the project creating process is describing with picture step by step(Figure 5.2).

Figure 5.2: Visual studio project creation

We need to install and then open our IDE called visual studio. Here we can select or create ASP.Net MVC project and then can working with it. We can create many types of project in visual studio but my task is about the ASP.NET MVC so I select the project as a MVC project like this(Figure 5.3).

Figure 5.3: Selection the type of project

After selecting the MVC project we will find that there are three types of folders. One is model, another is View and a controller folder. In my project I also worked with these three folders. Here is the screenshot of my project MVC folders (Figure 5.4).

So at first we need to make a model class by seeing the signup page registration field. Here I give the signup page design and field (Figure 5.5).

From the picture we saw that there are a total of eight fields for registering a user. Fields are FirstName, LastName, Email, Password, Gender, Day, Month, Year. So for this specific every field we need to specify or write fields into our Model class so here are the fields I create into the model class which is shown in the below picture (Figure 5.6).

Then I made a controller called AccountController. This controller is made for controlling those field data which is collected from the signup form. Then match them with some logic. If all of the logic is required then the controller will store data to the database and successfully register the user (Figure 5.7).

Here is the view for the landing page. From this page all of the data is requested to the controller. Then the controller matches with the model and then checks the logic for storing that data to the database. The landing page view code is given (Figure 5.8)

This is the total process of how the MVC pattern works. I followed the total process and pattern for my task. And at last I completed the total task they wanted. They liked my work and gave me an agreement paper for doing work into their company, Glostars, as an ASP.NET Full Stack developer.

Figure 5.4: MVC folders in project

Figure 5.5: Signup popup page for registration

```

AccountViewModels.cs * X
glostars.Models.RegisterViewModel - BirthdayMonth
66 public class RegisterViewModel
67 {
68     [Required]
69     [EmailAddress]
70     [Display(Name = "Email")]
71     public string Email { get; set; }
72
73     [Required]
74     [StringLength(100, ErrorMessage = "The {0} must be at least {2} characters long.", MinimumLength = 8)]
75     [DataType(DataType.Password)]
76     [Display(Name = "password")]
77     public string Password { get; set; }
78
79     [Required]
80     [Display(Name = "Last Name")]
81     public string LastName { get; set; }
82
83     [Required]
84     [Display(Name = "Name")]
85     public string Name { get; set; }
86
87     [Required]
88     [Display(Name = "Gender")]
89     public string Gender { get; set; }
90
91     [Required]
92     [Display(Name = "Day")]
93     public int BirthdayDay { get; set; }
94
95     [Required]
96     [Display(Name = "Month")]
97     public int BirthdayMonth { get; set; }
98

```

Figure 5.6: RegisterViewModel Class

```

[HttpPost]
[AllowAnonymous]
public async Task<string> Signup(RegisterViewModel model)
{
    var listError = new ArrayList();
    var user = new ApplicationUser
    {
        Name = model.Name,
        LastName = model.LastName,
        Gender = model.Gender,
        UserName = model.Email,
        Email = model.Email,
        Birthday = new DateTime(model.BirthdayYear, model.BirthdayMonth, model.BirthdayDay),
        UseDefaultPicture = true
    };
    if (user.age() < 13)
    {
        listError.Add("age_restriction,You should be at least 13 years old to sign up");
        return JsonConvert.SerializeObject(new
        {
            result = false,
            ErrorMsg = listError
        });
    }
    var result = await UserManager.CreateAsync(user, model.Password);
    if (result.Succeeded)
    {
        await SendEmailConfirmationCode(user.Id, "Confirm your account");
        ViewBag.Message =
            "Check your email and confirm your account, you must be confirmed before you can log in.";
    }
}

```

Figure 5.7: Controller for Register Model

```

LandingPageIndex.html AccountController AccountViewModels
1 @using Resources
2
3 ViewBag.Title = "LandingPage";
4 Keynote = "~/Content/Shared/_Layout.cshtml?class=1";
5
6
7 @div class="signupPortion"
8 @if (User.IsAuthenticated)
9 @if (User.IsAuthenticated)
10 @if (User.IsAuthenticated)
11 @if (User.IsAuthenticated)
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```

Figure 5.8: View for the landing page

Chapter 6

Implementation

This section is called implementation where I am going to describe the details work what I have done into the glostars and how I implement the logic and design into their website. As I already mentioned into the project background section now I am going to describe all of the things below:

6.1 The Interview Task

They give me a website page which is created by using only HTML, CSS. My task was that I need to convert this design to the ASP.Net design and then connect it to the backend server. There existing project is created with using the technology which is ASP.NET MVC, AngularJS, SignalR, ASP.NET web API. But for the task I need to know how the asp.net website work and the MVC pattern. And the visual studio IDE tools. Into the design there is some functionality I need to work for.

Figure 6.1: upper part of the landing page

Figure 6.2: middle part of the landing page

Figure 6.3: lower part of the landing page

This is the total full page they give me. The task is simple I need to register a user by clicking the signup button fill up the registration form and then Login in that user to the website. For doing this task at first I made a project in visual studio and then select the MVC project. Here MVC is a design pattern. It is a most famous design pattern which is used for software development nowadays (Figure 6.1 6.2 6.3).

MVC: It means (model- view –controller) this three different portion has different work. Model makes the class for the filed we want to store into the database. Then controller which controls the Model and View portion. Controllers main work is to connect the Model and View using the help of data base.

For my task I follow the pattern I made a RegisterViewModel class into the model folder for user registration. Then made a AccountController class into the controller folder also a view which is into the view folder that file is

called landingpage. It is a html file. I am working at Asp.net so I need to convert this html to the cshtml.

6.2 Task 1

6.2.1 Problem 1

First work is that I need to re-design their website. They have some UI design but which is developed using only html css and javascript. My work is that I want to use that design and then implement it to their existing website. So at first I need to convert full design into the Asp design which is called cshtml. I am going to share some screen shots of my work what I need to do and also numbering the work they need from me as a first work.

- I have to change the whole landing page of their website.
- I need to change the navigation bar of their full website.
- Change the notification button icon
- After changing the design I have to connect all of them with Asp.net MVC and backend server.
- Change the navigation or menu bar after login all page and before login all pages.

So I start to solve one by one requirement. I already showed the landing page picture. So I need to implement the landing page replacing their existing landing page. So the landing page design code they give me. but it was made with bootstrap 4 version . But their website already used bootstrap3 version so there is a confliction between this two version. That was a huge problem and it takes about a week to solve this problem.

6.2.2 Solution 1

For solving this problem I made the design with bootstrap 3 again. Because they give me the version of bootstrap 4 design which will not support into their website. So I took the responsibilities and made the design into bootstrap version 3 for solving this confliction problem. They also give me a code of navigation bar but that was not worked because that was also made in bootstrap version 4 . so for the work I need to code it into bootstrap version

Figure 6.4: Before login navigation bar pic

Figure 6.5: After login navigation bar pic

3. Here is the navigation bar picture which I code and designed in bootstrap version 3 given in (Figure 6.4 6.5)

This two navigation bar I re-designed in bootstrap 3 for matching our version and remove the conflicting between bootstrap 3 and 4. After our design part is ready then I converted it into asp design for connecting with backend. Here I use the design pattern MVC . I created a view and layout.cshtml file for adding those design and then merge them with their existing website. I read all of the code of their existing project find out those lines which is written for that navigation bars. So I replace the code of landing page and this two navigation bars for all of the page of the website and placed them correctly. Here is the sample code for the navigation bar given below I collect this photo from my project work (Figure 6.6).

```

1 @using Glostars.Models
2
3
4 <nav class="navbar navbar-inverse navbar-custom navbar-fixed-top">
5   <div class="container-fluid">
6     <div class="navbar-header">
7       <button id="nav-close" type="button" class="navbar-toggle" data-toggle="collapse" data-target="#myNavbar">
8         <span class="icon-bar"></span>
9         <span class="icon-bar"></span>
10        <span class="icon-bar"></span>
11      </button>
12
13      <div class="logo">
14        <a href="/Account/SignIn">
15          
16        </a>
17      </div>
18    </div>
19    <div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="myNavbar">
20      <ul class="nav navbar-nav navbar-right">
21        <li><a href="/Login/new/LoginViewModel()">
22          @Html.Raw("Login")
23        </li>
24      </ul>
25    </div>
26  </div>
27 </nav>

```

Figure 6.6: Navigation bar code sample

In this way I solved all the requirement of my First work and also delivery the all of the work in time to our Glostars company CEO. Basically he maintain the whole developers work of all employees. After finishing my first work they give me more requirements for fix that problem that means they give me the bugs for solving it. I used debugging tools for solving that all

bugs (Figure 6.7).

Debugging Tools

- I used visual studio debugging tools for testing c# code.
- For the Frontend debugging I used Google chrome Inspect Element that will help us for find out the problem and also solving the problem by using it.

Figure 6.7: Google chrome Inspect debug Tools

6.3 Task 2

When I have done their website work there was some bugs out there. So they find out those bugs and give me those bugs for solving it.

6.3.1 Problem 1

When a user try to register the register form should be validate that time.

6.3.2 Solution 1

For handling validation Register page which is popup when we click into the Signup button. We can validate a form in many ways such as “html required” validation or “Validation in Model Class”. I used Html Required validation for doing the task. Here is the screen shot when I fix that bug (Figure 6.8).

Figure 6.8: Validation of register form

6.3.3 Problem 2

Change the Background picture of the landing page.

6.3.4 Solution 2

For changing the background picture I am just replace the picture with the new picture into the code and successfully done this requirement.

6.3.5 Problem 3

Change the content of the landing page.

6.3.6 Solution 3

Into Some html tag I changed the content for the landing page website. The content basically they give me for their website (Figure 6.9).

Figure 6.9: Content of the landing page photo

6.3.7 Problem 4

Change the About, FAQ, Contact Us, Media Page Navigation Bar.

6.3.8 Solution 4

For Changing About, FAQ, Contact Us, Media page navigation bar I made a different layout page into the view folder which will common in all of this four page and then call that layout page to the other html page. In this way I solved the problem of all this pages navigation bar. Here is the difference we can find out if we see these two picture where I showed the before bug on the page and after solving the bug of that four pages (Figure 6.10 6.11).

Figure 6.10: Before solving bug

6.3.9 Problem 5

Change the color of signup button from red to green color.

6.3.10 Solution 5

Changing the color of the signup button from red to green I only change the css file code where the color is given for that button is red. I just replace it with Green. In this way button color changed into green.

Figure 6.11: After solving bug

6.3.11 Problem 6

Into the Signup popup terms of use button not working.

6.3.12 Solution 6

For solving this requirement I need to learn the bootstrap 3 modal. Which is basically used for popup effect into the website. So I learned the popup effect into bootstrap 3. Then I liked that popup which the button terms of use into the signup form and successfully It's working.

6.4 Task 3

After solving all of the problem they give me more bugs which is more challenging tasks for me. They give the task of changing some design of their website. And the requirements they want to solve which is given below.

6.4.1 Problem 1

Into the Landing Page there is a problem in navigation bar which is, it so close in left side and it should be more on right side.

6.4.2 Solution 1

Basically there is a html tag called “ul” that means unordered list. And that portion is given so much margin into the left side in the css file. So I just minimize the margin size from the css code and solve the problem so easily (Figure 6.12).

Figure 6.12: Navigation Bar

6.4.3 Problem 2

After Login navigation bar have two things which is Search bar and Upload button it should be more left side.

6.4.4 Solution 2

At first when I implement the new design to the glostars website the problem is occurred at that time. After log into the glostars website the navigation bar there is a search and upload button. But it is more right side. This problem is like as number 1 problem. By the same way I solved that problem. Just changed the css code from the css file which is "margin-right : -22px;" (Figure 6.13).

Figure 6.13: Search & Upload Button

6.4.5 Problem 3

After responsive the navigation bar name should be on beside of the profile pic into the nav bar.

6.4.6 Solution 3

After responsive the navigation bar name should be on beside of the profile pic into the nav bar. At first the name was a different section from profile pic section . but it has a problem when we minimize the website the name of the user is not showed beside the profile pic circle. But after solving the html tag and replace the name into the code then it showed beside the propic circle (Figure 6.14).

Figure 6.14: Minimized Nav Bar

6.4.7 Problem 4

Upload Button should response more faster than now.

6.4.8 Solution 4

Upload button from the navigation bar was not working fast at the time when my work was published on the server. But there is no problem with that button. The main problem is happened from the server. When anything is published on the server, the server response late at that time. After some time passed the server become more faster and upload button automatically working faster. So this is the solve of the requirement 4.

6.4.9 Problem 5

Remove the IOS App link from the Landing page.

6.4.10 Solution 5

For Removing the IOS logo and link I am just commenting the html line. So when it is commented then it will not execute into the landing page so the ios link will vanished at that time (Figure 6.15).

Figure 6.15: Removing IOS logo code

6.4.11 Problem 6

There is a line beside to the Recognition valued user. Need to remove that line which defect into the design.

6.4.12 Solution 6

When I solved all of the 10 requirement. They find out more problems that means bugs so I need to solve that problem too. If I have no knowledge about html, css, javascript, c# then it will not possible to fix this requirements. But I can solve that because I know all of those things. And its so comfortable for me. So next bugs which is given from the glostars is described below.

6.4.13 Problem 7

In every page navigation bar should be fixed on the top. If we scroll the mouse button it should not fade away.

6.4.14 Solution 7

For solving this problem I need to know the position tag on css. By using Position attribute we can solve this bug so easily. All of the pages has nav bar which is called “{nav;” tag in html. So for this html tag I need to add a css position attribute for fix that nav bar. So I write “position:fixed”. This code basically solved my problem. After doing this all of the pages are locked

at the top of the page. when I scroll the page navigation bar didn't fade out at time (Figure 6.16).

Figure 6.16: Nav Bar Scroll

6.4.15 Problem 8

There is no hover effect on power button and upload button.

6.4.16 Solution 8

Into this section when I added navigation bar to the website there is no hover effect into the upload button. Hover basically a css attribute which make a button shadow effect or background effect. So I make a hover effect for that upload button to the css file and solved the problem by adding the effect (Figure 6.17).

Figure 6.17: Hover Effect Upload Button

6.4.17 Problem 9

When minimize the Landing page it should be responsive like about page.

6.4.18 Solution 9

When minimize the Landing page it should be responsive like about page. The main problem is that landing page is not responsive properly that mans

its component have margin padding and bootstrap css problem that's why it didn't work properly. For fixing this problem I used the bootstrap css file where I found some problem into the code. Also the debugger tools notify me that there is problem in default bootstrap css file code. I opened that folder and file and customize the responsive section. There was some code taken extra margin padding from the left side that's why this problem occurred. After fixing the bug in css file margin padding section landing page responsiveness working properly (Figure 6.18).

Figure 6.18: Landing Page Responsive

6.4.19 Problem 10

There is a button in navigation bar on about page when it clicked it don't response so need to fix it.

6.4.20 Solution 10

For solving this problem used a "Jquery" code which basically handle all the action things. Jquery is Javascript library . By using Jquery its really easy to handle any html tag . Jquery had many default function like click, fade, disply, animation etc. So I used the click function and add a logic that if it clicked then it will open the options of login otherwise it will not opened anything. At first this Jquery library is not implemented into our project. For this reason that problem occurred into the navigation bar (Figure 6.19 6.20).

Figure 6.19: Before fix dropdown response button

6.5 Task 4

6.5.1 Problem 1

When click in notification button all of the time zone gone down from the box.

Figure 6.20: After fix dropdown response button

6.5.2 Solution 1

It's a simple problem I found out that is there is section called span which is a html tag. On that tag the time is stored. So I am just customize that span tag . I added the time span to that span so that they don't break separately. So after doing this work all of the problem just solved . All the time is showed into the notification bar when we clicked it (Figure 6.21).

6.5.3 Problem 2

After searching something in search button there is a section called 'see all people' but its not working properly.

6.5.4 Solution 2

After searching some user into the search bar we will see a section that is called "see all people". When we click into that section there is no page behind that button so nothing is happened when we click that button. For solving that problem I made a section for that button and when I click that button all of the user is showed into that page. Its simple solving section I just made a view into our project and add the user to that page (Figure 6.22).

Figure 6.21: Time zone issue

6.5.5 Problem 3

In the Url Home/glostarsphoto navigation bar is not changed.

6.5.6 Problem 4

Into the Url Home/Prizes page change two section one is Sep-Dec 2017 and another section should be written in Updated on Oct 2017

6.5.7 Problem 5

Into the Url Home/Notifications there navigation bar should be changed.

6.5.8 Problem 6

When clicking any hashtag there navigation bar is old. Also the same problem in search result page.

6.5.9 Solution 3 4 5 6

All of this bugs have same problem. All of this pages do not have the layout of new navigation bar. So I selected them individually and then replace the

Figure 6.22: See all people issue solve

old layout html file with the new layout file. So after changing layout file all the pages have new navigation bar(Figure 6.23 6.24).

Figure 6.23: Navigation old layout

Figure 6.24: Navigation new layout

Changes happened into the notification page navigation bar (Figure 6.25 6.26).

Changes into the glostars photo page which is the navigation bar before it was look like pink color and new design it look like violet color and some functionalities changed (Figure 6.27 6.28).

6.5.10 Problem 7

Need to change the star color from pink to violet.

6.5.11 Solution 7

When anyone upload a photo other user can rating that photo by giving them star. It is just like face book like system. But my work is that I need

Figure 6.25: Before the notification page

Figure 6.26: Before the notification page

Figure 6.27: glostars photo page before

Figure 6.28: glostars photo page after

to change that star color from pick to violet. So for this I find out the code from the project where that star color is given as pink. At last I found out from the css file and then I change it to the color violet (Figure 6.29 6.30).

Figure 6.29: Rating color red

Figure 6.30: Star color violet

So this is the all requirement they give me to solve. I solved all of the bugs and made them happy with my work.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Recommendations

7.1 Conclusion

Internship program provides a chance to the students to implement the theoretical knowledge in the tough real world environments. This internship program in 12th Semester arranged by Department of Computer Science and Engineering gives me a chance to implement the theoretical knowledge which has been learned last 3.5 years. This is a new experience which provides the opportunity of self-assessments. What I learn from the internship and why it was important are following

- It was a opportunity to “test drive” a career (would I be happier in this platform or should I change my motto)
- Accumulating new skills
- Gaining a “real world” perspective on an occupation
- To gain confidence
- Career-relevant internship experience will make a better impression on my resume.
- To build motivation and work habits.
- To build my network through whom I met in an internship. I hope that, in future this experience will very helpful for my professional life.

7.2 Recommendations

All this recommendation are based on my personal working experience.

7.2.1 Recommendation to their services

- They need to upgrade their website service to attract more clients.
- They need to change their System architectural design so that they can make their system faster to attract more customers.
- They should add helps and suggestion section for customer to improve service.

7.2.2 Recommendation to software & hardware services

- All of the hardware they used is well but they should upgrade it into SSD so that it will more faster than now.
- They are totally depending on Microsoft its really well but if they have the scope of open source then it will be more better.

7.2.3 Recommendation to other services

- Internet service should be upgraded to increase data speed.
- In dhanmondi branch, there should be more employees to decrease work load.
- There should be more effectiveness in record keeping.
- There is no official website for dhanmondi branch & I think this mandatory for every bank nowadays.
- There should be a more effective training program for junior level employee.

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Declaration

This internship report is submitted to the Computer Science and Engineering, University of Liberal Arts Bangladesh in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the project course of Bachelor of Science. So, I hereby, declare that this internship report is based on the surveys found by me. Materials of work found by other researchers are mentioned by reference. This internship report, neither in whole, nor in part, has been previously submitted for any internship report or course.

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